

inhabited by tribal people. The terraced lands vary widely in ecological and agronomic systems, ranging from moisture-stressed upland conditions to wet lowland conditions. On the basis of moisture and water regimes the lands are classified into six groups: Tanr 1, Tanr 2, Tanr 3, Don 3, Don 2, and Don 1. The Tanr lands are subject to moisture stress, which is most severe in Tanr 1 followed by that in Tanr 2 and 3. Don 1 lands are waterlogged throughout the cropping season, while Don 3 and 2 depend on rainfall for moisture.

A rich variability of cultivated rice is found in those systems. Annual and perennial wild rices of the *O. sativa* type are also common. The Gora rices (early

maturing) are grown in Tanr lands in Ranchi district. The well-known Black Gora has primitive characteristics, i.e., black hulls and red kernels. Annual wild rices (similar to *O. nivara*) are also frequently observed in the fields of Black Gora. They have black hulls, red kernels, and awned spikelets. Their grains tend to shatter. The wild rices show some similarities to Black Gora.

In Chaibasa district, annual wild rices, some with black and others with straw hulls, are found near rice fields. Semisterile annual wild rices that appear to be hybrids with *O. sativa* are also common in some regions. A few cultivated rices such as Chidikata, Koya, and Kosambaba have certain characters

similar to those of annual wild rices - black hulls, awns, and red kernels. Kosambaba has both straw and black hulls. In one instance, Chidikata was observed with black as well as with golden brown hulls. A few varieties also had intravarietal variations.

Such rices as Black Gora, Chidikata, Koya, and Kosambaba that the tribal people cultivate appear to be primitive cultivars with many of the characters of their nearby wild relatives. Such varieties could be valuable in understanding genetic interrelationships; they could offer opportunities for the study of the affinity of the cultivated rices and their adjoining wild relatives. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Hardness and stickiness of cooked rice as indicators of eating quality

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Methods of measuring stickiness and hardness of cooked rice with an Instron food tester were developed using 20 g raw milled rice cooked in an optimum amount of water based on amylose content. Stickiness was measured as the work required to separate the plunger from the platform with cooked rice pressed between them. Hardness was the maximum force required to extrude the cooked rice through a modified Ottawa Texture Measuring System extrusion cell. Both stickiness and hardness of cooked rice, mostly IRRI samples, correlated with amylose content (see figure). But the hardness values varied more than stickiness values for all amylose levels.

Among IRRI high-amylose (>25%) rices, the grain of those with soft gel consistency tends to be softer and more sticky when cooked. Varietal differences in texture among rices with low or intermediate amylose content were associated with differences in hardness

Relationship between amylose content of milled rice and Instron stickiness and hardness of rice cooked with the optimum level of water and then cooled. IRRI, 1977.

of cooked rice rather than with differences in stickiness. Among Philippine and Indonesian rices of intermediate amylose content (20–25%), samples with soft gel consistency and low amylograph consistency tended to be soft when cooked. In some cases, differences in hardness of cooked rice were associated with differences in gelatinization temperature of the starch (alkali spreading value). Among South Korean and Japanese low-amylose (12–20%) rices, hardness values of cooked rice were related mainly to differences in gel and amylograph consistency. When cooked, the preferred waxy varieties from Korea, Philippines, and Thailand were soft and sticky, and tended to have low (<70°C) gelatinization temperature. ❧

Properties of lintnerized starch granules from rices of different amylose content and gelatinization temperature

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The gelatinization temperature of starch is rapidly becoming recognized as an important indicator of eating quality of both waxy (glutinous) and nonwaxy rices. Its measurement in breeding programs by

Recovery of lintnerized starch from starch granules of eight rices differing in amylose content and final gelatinization temperature.

the alkali digestibility test on whole kernels of milled rice suggests that the whole kernel also reflects this starch property. To better understand the property, the characteristics of starch granules of eight rices differing in amylose content and gelatinization temperature were studied at IRRI. The rices were lintnerized or corroded in 2.2 N HCl at 35°C for 15 days. Lintnerization of rice starch granules consisted of a fast stage of 7 to 9 days involving the amorphous portion of the granules, and of a slower stage involving the crystalline portion. The weight recovery of lintnerized starch ranged from 6.6 to 21.1% and was greater for samples with higher gelatinization temperature (>70°C) and, to a lesser extent, high amylose content (see figure). Lintnerized starch had sharper X-ray diffraction peaks (more crystalline) than native starch. At the same amylose content, rice starch granules with high gelatinization temperature had a greater crystalline fraction than those with low gelatinization temperature.

The residual starch from both waxy and nonwaxy rices consisted mainly of two fractions with about 15 and 30 glucose units. The 15-glucose-unit fraction was linear and corresponded to the size of the outer chain length of rice amylopectin. The fraction consisting of 30 glucose units was probably a mixture of singly branched and linear dextrans, as indicated by the incomplete debranching into the 15-glucose-unit

fraction by pullulanase. Differences in mean molecular size of the lintnerized starch (19 to 30 glucose units) were due to differences in the ratio of those two fractions. Thus, differences in

gelatinization temperature of starch granules and their accessibility to various chemicals such as HCl and KOH were verified to be related to degree of crystallinity of the granules. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Occurrence of rice tungro virus in Tamil Nadu

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Rice tungro is caused by a virus that is known to be transmitted by leafhopper vectors. In recent years tungro has been epidemic or epiphytotic, often striking suddenly and devastating large areas of rice. The existence of tungro in India remained obscure until 1969, when a severe epidemic took a heavy toll of the rice crops in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar.

A tungro outbreak was noticed in this tract during kharif (July–Oct.) and pishanam (Nov.–Mar. 1977–78), seasons of 1977. The disease was observed in severe proportions in the southern districts of Tamil Nadu — Ramnathapuram, Madurai, Tirunelveli, and Kanyakumari. The disease incidence was severe in rice varieties ADT 31, TKM 8, TN1, IR8, IR5, ASD 11, Co 40, Co 25, and Bhavani — but IR20 was completely disease free. Ponni, Culture AS 3827, Culture AS 1391, and eight other entries — 1201, 1203, 1205, 1208, 1209, 1217, 1219, and 1230 — were found moderately resistant to tungro. ❧

A possible source of resistance to rice ragged stunt disease

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Preliminary results of a search for sources of resistance to rice ragged stunt disease reveal that the variety Ptb 21 Acc. no. 11053 received from the Central Rice Research Institute of India may be resistant; it consistently had a low percentage of seedling infection after ragged stunt inoculation by viruliferous

brown planthopper (BPH) *Maparvatu fugens* in screen cages and in a screenhouse.

The resistance of this Ptb 21 sample to BPH has not been determined, but another Ptb 21 sample Acc. no. 6113 received from the Andhra Pradesh Agricultural Research Institute in Hyderabad is known to be resistant to all three known BPH biotypes. Hence, Ptb 21 Acc. no. 11053 may also be resistant to BPH. Even so, the low percentage of seedlings of Ptb 21 Acc. no. 11053 infected with ragged

Infection of rice seedlings with ragged stunt disease after inoculation by two methods. IRRI, 1978.

Acc. no.	Variety	Seedlings infected with ragged stunt (%)		Brown planthopper resistance ^a
		Cage method	Screenhouse method	
105	TN1	92	96	S
7733	Gangala	71	84	R
6113	Ptb 21	—	—	R
11053	Ptb 21	3	12	—

^aAt IRRI Entomology Department. S = susceptible; R = resistant; — = data not available.